

EPIDEMIOLOGY, PATHOGENETIC MECHANISMS, CLASSIFICATION, DIAGNOSTICS AND BASIC CONCEPTS OF TREATMENT OF OBESITY AGAINST THE BACKGROUND OF TYPE 2 DIABETES MELLITUS (TYPE 2 DM) (LITERATURE REVIEW)

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Abstract. Obesity is a chronic multifactorial disease, heterogeneous in etiology and clinical manifestations, progressing in the natural course and characterized by excessive deposition of adipose tissue in the body [4].

All over the world, today there is a tendency to consume "fast food" products (fast foods, hamburgers, cheeseburgers, etc.) and a decrease in physical activity due to the increase in the number of "sedentary" professions and growing urbanization [4;17;18].

Keywords: clinical manifestation, obesity, concomitant disease, adipose tissue, coronary artery disease.

According to WHO, in 2016, almost 2 billion people were overweight, of which more than 650 million were diagnosed with obesity [34; 37; 40; 46], which is accompanied by an increase in the number of patients with concomitant diseases, and, accordingly, mortality [28; 39; 42; 44]. In modern conditions, obesity and type 2 diabetes are a medical problem that is of a pandemic nature, is associated with an increased risk of morbidity and mortality, and requires new approaches to treatment [4; 27]. Such a rapid increase in the incidence of diabetes was the reason for the adoption of UN Resolution 61/225 of 20.12.2006 on diabetes mellitus, and in 2011 - the UN Political Declaration addressed to national health systems as one of the leading causes of disability and mortality of the population [5; 15; 21]. Thus, obesity in combination with type 2 diabetes is the cause of renal failure in 40-55% of cases, coronary artery disease and the cause of lower limb amputations in 50-60% of cases, which reduces the life expectancy and quality of life of the population [2; 3; 14].

Type 2 diabetes mellitus (hereinafter referred to as type 2 DM) (non-insulin-dependent diabetes) is an endocrine disease associated with insulin resistance. This is the body's insensitivity to its own hormone insulin, the level of which is normal or even elevated. The disease most often occurs in people who are obese. With type 2 DM, normal glucose levels are maintained in the blood due to increased insulin production. At the initial stages, tablet medications are prescribed that increase the susceptibility of cells to insulin or enhance its production in the pancreas. To compensate for the elevated glucose level, the body begins to quickly excrete it through the kidneys with urine. High sugar levels in biological fluids provoke an increase in osmotic pressure, which leads to profuse urination and dehydration. The main symptoms of diabetes are related to this - thirst, weakness, dry skin. The compensatory capabilities of the pancreas and the body are exhausted over time, the synthesis of the hormone declines. As a result, patients are forced to switch to insulin injections, which indicates the development of secondary insulin dependence.

Pathogenesis of obesity development. The main mechanism leading to obesity is the pathological deposition of adipocytes, which leads to an increase in MT [32].

Insulin resistance is directly related to the deposition of visceral adipose tissue, which leads to hyperinsulinemia, which, in turn, ultimately contributes to the development of dyslipidemia [33].

The role of the hypothalamus is being actively studied [20; 35; 45]. The role of the hormone leptin is actively being studied [24; 38]. The peptide hormone ghrelin also plays an important role in the pathogenesis of obesity [24].

And, undoubtedly, Dedov I.I. et al. (2016) are right, who note the complexity and diversity of the pathogenesis of obesity, which determines the possibility of developing various treatment methods [5].

Large studies have proven that obesity is a risk factor for comorbid conditions [1; 6]. Obesity is often accompanied by dyslipidemia, one of the causes of which is hyperinsulinemia [1;8;36].

Mechanisms associated with improvement of glycemic indices after bariatric surgeries. The main problem in studying the mechanisms responsible for improvement of type 2 DM after surgical treatment is the difficulty of separating the effects of bariatric surgeries caused by weight loss and those not associated with weight loss.

The introduction of complex bypass surgeries (gastric bypass, biliopancreatic bypass) into practice has shown that weight loss is only one of the factors in improving carbohydrate metabolism. Postoperative reduction of glycemia level to significant weight loss indicates involvement of other mechanisms in this process [26]. Moreover, remission of type 2 diabetes with the same weight loss depends on the method of surgical intervention [30].

Two hypotheses have been proposed to understand this phenomenon. The first, the “low small intestine hypothesis”, is based on the assumption that as a result of accelerated movement of the food bolus to the distal parts of the small intestine, stimulation of L-cells and rapid release of antidiabetogenic and anorexigenic factors occur [43].

An alternative “high small bowel or anti-incretin hypothesis” is that excluding the duodenum and proximal jejunum for the passage of food masses may prevent the secretion of a hypothetical “anti-incretin” that stimulates the development of insulin resistance and type 2 diabetes [41]. Thus, both hypotheses are based on an understanding of the special role of the incretin system in improving metabolic control in patients with type 2 DM after bariatric surgeries [23].

Clinical observations show that intestinal malabsorption caused by bypass operations leads to a decrease in the intensity of glucose absorption, which minimizes pancreatic β -cell stress, and a decrease in fat absorption reduces the circulation of free fatty acids, which leads to increased tissue sensitivity to insulin [12;29].

Classification and etiology of obesity development. According to the classification by Dedova I.I. (2018), obesity is of the following types:

- 1) exogenous-constitutional obesity, which is observed in only 10% of cases;
- 2) symptomatic (secondary) obesity, which accounts for 90% of cases [4].

The BMI is usually calculated using a standardized formula:

where I – the body mass index;

m – the body weight in kg;

h – the height in meters.

Units of measurement — kg/m^2 [4].

Classification of obesity by BMI (WHO, 1997, with supplement). Type of body mass BMI: normal body mass; overweight; obesity stage I; obesity stage II; obesity stage III.

Factors determining the development of obesity include:

- 1) psychological and behavioral;
- 2) demographic;
- 3) socio-economic;
- 4) hereditary predisposition [33].

Diagnostics. Patients with obesity against the background of type 2 DM are subject to standard examination. Taking into account comorbid conditions, duration and severity of the disease, the diagnostic plan can be adjusted individually. Nevertheless, there is a list of mandatory procedures, which include: coagulogram; chest X-ray; general blood and urine tests; abdominal ultrasound; ECG; blood biochemistry; gastroscopy, etc. [<https://www.medicina.ru.>, 2024].

General principles of initiation and intensification of hypoglycemic therapy. The basis of treatment is lifestyle changes:

rational nutrition and increased physical activity, stratification of treatment tactics depending on the initial level of HbA1c, identified when diagnosing type 2 DM;

personalization of the choice of hypoglycemic drugs depending on the dominant clinical problem.

Monitoring the effectiveness of hypoglycemic therapy by the level of HbA1c is carried out every 3 months.

Evaluation of the rate of decrease in HbA1c. Changing (intensifying) hypoglycemic therapy in case of its ineffectiveness (i.e. in the absence of achievement of individual HbA1c goals) is carried out no later than after 6 months [5].

Lifestyle changes using drug therapy are not an effective method of treating obesity. According to the US National Institute of Health, after bariatric surgery, 40% of patients maintain a reduced body weight for 5 years, and with morbid obesity - only 5-10% [31].

Therefore, at present, one of the most effective methods of weight loss are bariatric (from the Greek baros - heavy, obese) surgeries.

The use of bariatric surgery improves the course of type 2 DM, allows for remission or a reduction in the dose of hypoglycemic drugs. It reduces the amount of adipose tissue, reduces the load on the cardiovascular system, as well as on the joints. However, after bariatric surgery, weight gain may occur again, so active lifelong participation of the patients themselves in regular monitoring after surgery is necessary [11]. At the Second Congress, held in Paris in 1855, Farr and d'Espine presented two separate lists, classification of causes of death, based on completely different principles. In 1864, this classification was revised, which is now known as the International Classification of Diseases (ICD) [10].

The basic concept of treating obesity using bariatric surgery is to suppress the synthesis of the hunger hormone (ghrelin) and reduce absorption from the gastrointestinal tract.

There are more than 40 different types of bariatric surgeries, conventionally divided into 3 groups [4]: 1) surgeries that limit the amount of food consumed - restrictive surgeries (gastric banding, installation of an intragastric balloon, longitudinal resection of the stomach, gastroplication);

2) surgeries aimed at reducing the absorption area in the intestine, or malabsorptive (jejunoileal bypass and jejunoileal bypass). At the moment, they are of purely historical interest; 3) combined (mini-gastrobypass, Roux-en-Y gastric bypass, biliopancreatic bypass modified by Scopinaro, biliopancreatic bypass with duodenal switch modified by Hess – Marceau, biliopancreatic bypass (diversion) with a single duodenoileoanastomosis (SADI modification), etc.) [12;13;25].

Conclusion. Thus, in modern conditions, obesity and type 2 DM are a medical problem that is pandemic in nature, associated with an increased risk of morbidity and mortality, and requires new approaches to treatment. The effectiveness of conservative therapy is 5-10%. Therefore, surgical methods have become widely used throughout the world, which, however, are accompanied by postoperative complications, which indicates the need for further improvement of bariatric surgical interventions.

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